

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF RITONAVIR SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET BY USING WET GRANULATION TECHNIQUE

¹Dr. Nansri saha, ²M. Umadevi, ²Nidhi Sahu, ²R. Shiva Krishna, ²Sony Kumari, ²Syed Baqtiyar Ali

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, SSJ College of Pharmacy, V.N Pally, Hyderabad, Telangana.

²Pharmaceutics JNTUH -SSJCP, Hyderabad, Telangana-500075.

Received: Jun 9, 2025

Accepted: Jul 7, 2025

Published: Jul 8, 2025

ABSTRACTA

The purpose of present study was to develop, optimize a sustained release drug delivery formulation for oral drug delivery system of ritonavir in order to ensure maximum controlled drug release. Oral solid dosage forms are the preferred administration route for many drugs especially for modified release product. In sustained release technology, tablets compressed by wet granulation technique are the most attractive both scientifically and economically. Among the different polymers used for this purpose, HPMC have been used successfully to obtain appropriate sustained release formulation of ritonavir. (Oral drug delivery is the most widely utilized route of administration among all the routes that have been explored for the systemic delivery of drug via pharmaceutical products of different dosage form. Oral route is considered most natural, uncomplicated, convenient and safe due to its ease of administration, patient acceptance and cost-effective manufacturing process. The goal of a sustained release dosage form is to maintain therapeutic blood or tissue levels of the drug for an extended and specified period of time. In this study, sustained release Ritonavir tablets with different polymers such as HPMC, carbopol, EC were prepared by wet granulation technique. They were then studied with regards to their release behavior. The appropriate formulation from the series was chosen and best fitted equations for their release were suggested. The effect of different polymers on the release rate of the drug was evaluated and compared to each other (formulation with EC, HPMC, and Carbopol). The rate of drug release from the formulation containing HPMC (F₂) was more when compared to Carbopol and EC.

INTRODUCTION:

A sustained drug delivery system (SR) is a drug delivery method that can produce a gradual release of a medicine over an extended period of time. The dose form of SR received greater attention because of the oral route's versatility. A single dosage of a medication is more advantageous than several doses since it is released over a longer period of time. The major objective is to increase patient compliance and the drug's efficacy for usage by achieving a stable plasma concentration of the medication in the blood. The simplest method for creating SR dosage forms is to create a matrix tablet for extended release (SR).¹

The oral bioavailability of medications with site-specific absorption from the stomach or upper portion of the small intestine is improved when drug delivery systems are kept in the stomach for a longer period of time. In order to achieve gastric residence duration for prolonged drug release, many strategies have been put forth to keep the dosage form in the stomach, including delayed gastric emptying devices, bioadhesive systems, and swelling and expanding systems.² Any medication delivery system's objective is to deliver a therapeutic dosage to the right location in the body in order to quickly and sustain the required drug concentration.³ By continually releasing medication over a prolonged period of time following the administration of a single dose, sustained release dosage forms allow for this intentional management of drug release, extending the therapeutic benefit.⁴

Including it in a matrix system is the most often used technique to control the sustained drug release. In order to achieve a desired drug release profile, cost-effectiveness, and widespread regulatory approval, hydrophilic polymer matrix solutions are frequently utilized in oral controlled drug delivery due to their versatility.⁵ Additionally, matrix systems are preferred over conventional drug delivery (TDS), which has several disadvantages such as recurrent administration and blood concentration fluctuations, because to their ease of use and patient compliance. The drug is uniformly distributed throughout the crosslink matrix of the linear polymer chain in this kind of drug delivery system.⁶ This kind of drug delivery method is thought to release the drug molecule from the matrix by dissolving it and then allowing it to diffuse through the polymer structure.⁷ As the

medication is released, solid particles start to disappear and the diffusion distance increases. If not prepared correctly, the majority of highly water-soluble medications may release the drug more quickly and are likely to result in dangerous concentrations.⁸ When creating sustained-release formulations of extremely water-soluble medications, hydrophilic polymers have emerged as the preferred product.⁹ The polymer expands when the dissolving medium or biological fluid enters the dosage form, and drug molecules start to diffuse out of the system at a rate that is dictated by the formulation method and the polymer's type and composition.¹⁰ Ritonavir is a bioactive antiretroviral medication used to treat viral infections including HIV/AIDS. belongs to Class II of the biopharmaceutical categorization system and, as a result of its limited water solubility, has a low and variable oral bioavailability. Ritonavir inhibits both the HIV-1 and HIV-2 proteases peptidomimetic¹¹.

Fig no.1 Structure of Ritonavir¹²

Ritonavir's short biological half-life (three to five hours), limited bioavailability (65%), narrow therapeutic index, and the fact that it is mostly absorbed from the stomach need controlled release¹³. All of the disadvantages made it necessary to create mucoadhesive microspheres to improve dosage form residency in the GIT. These microspheres could use all of ritonavir's effectiveness, which would lower the frequency of dose and increase bioavailability.

MATERIALS USED:

Ritonavir API was a gift sample, Hydroxy propyl Methyl cellulose, Carbapol, Ethyl cellulose as polymers, Microcrystalline cellulose and Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone 30 as binder, Magnesium stearate and Talc as Lubricant.

METHODOLOGY:

Selection of excipients to achieve the sustain release formulation of ritonavir sustain release tablet the following type of excipients are typically used.

Formulation by wet granulation method:

1) Drug and polymer mixing:

Weigh the required amount of ritonavir and sustain release polymer. Mix uniformly using blender.

2) Granulation:

Prepare a granulating solution or binder solution using pvpk30 dissolved in water add the binder solution slowly to the dry blend while mixing to form a wet granules.

3) Drying:

Dry the wet granules using a tray drying method at control temperature 40-50°C.

4) Milling and sizing:

Pass the dry granules from through a sieve number 20 or 40 mesh to get a uniform particle size.

5) Lubrication:

Blend the dry granules with magnesium stearate and talc for lubrication.

6) Compression into tablets:

Compress the granules by using 16 station tablet punching machine.

Here is a flow chart for the formulation of tablets by the Wet Granulation Method:**Tablet Formulation by Wet Granulation – Flow Chart:****Experimental methods:****A) STANDARD CALIBRATION CURVE OF RITONAVIR USING 6.8 PHOSPHATE BUFFER:**

Instrument: A double beam UV/VISIBLE spectrophotometer with a pair of 1cm quart 2 cells for reading absorbance.

1)Preparation of 6.8N phosphate buffer:

Place 75ml of 0.2M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate in a 250ml volumetric flask and add specific volume of 0.2M NaOH solution (22.4ml for PH 6.8) and then make up with water.

2)Preparation of standard stock solution:

50mg drug was taken accurately in a 50 ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved in 2ml of methanol and make up the volume 50ml with 6.8 phosphate buffer. (primary stock solution)

From the above solution 5ml of solution should be taken and dilute up to 50ml with 6.8 phosphate buffer (secondary stock solution)

The above stock solution dilute to below mention concentration. The absorbance was measured against 6.8 phosphate buffer as a blank at 239nm using UV spectrophotometer

↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓ ↓

1ml 2ml 3ml 4ml 5ml 6ml

10 µg/ml 20µg/ml 30µg/ml 40µg/ml 50µg/ml 60µg/ml

10 micro gram per ml: collect 1 ml from the the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer PH 6.8

20 micro gram per ml: collect 2ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer PH 6.8

30micro gram per ml: collect 3ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer PH 6.8

40 micro gram per ml: collect 4 ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to10 ml with phosphate buffer PH 6.8

50 micro gram per ml: collect 5ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8

60 micro gram per ml: collect 6ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer PH 6.8

B) STANDARD CALIBRATION CURVE OF RITONAVIR USING 0.1N HCL**Preparation of 0.1N HCL:**

Place 3.72gm of Potassium chloride in 250ml volumetric flask and add specific volume of 0.1N HCl (2.12ml for 0.1N) then make up with water.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

50mg drug was taken accurately in a 50 ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved in 2ml of methanol and make up the volume 50ml with 0.1N HCl

From the above solution 5ml of solution should be taken and dilute up to 50 ml with 0.1 N HCl (secondary stock solution)

The above stock solution dilute to below mention concentration. The absorbance was measured against 0.1N HCl as a blank at 239 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

10µg/ml 20µg/ml 30µg/ml 40µg/ml 50µg/ml 60µg/ml

10 micro gram per ml: collect 1 ml from the the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with acidic buffer PH 1.2

20 micro gram per ml: collect 2ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with acidic buffer PH 1.2

30micro gram per ml: collect 3ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with acidic buffer PH 1.2

40 micro gram per ml: collect 4 ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to10 ml with acidic buffer PH 1.2

50 micro gram per ml: collect 5ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with acidic buffer pH 1.2

60 micro gram per ml: collect 6ml from the above 50 ml solution and dilute to 10 ml with acidic buffer PH 1.2

Composition of Ritonavir tablet:

Table no.1 Composition of F1 to F6 ritonavir tablets formulation

Drug and excipients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Rtonavir	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg
HPMC	50mg	75mg	-	-	-	-
Carbopol	-	-	50mg	75mg	-	-
Ethyl cellulose	-	-	-	-	50mg	75mg
MCC	125mg	100mg	125mg	100mg	125mg	100mg
PVP K30	15mg	15mg	15mg	15mg	15mg	15mg
Magnesium stearate	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg
Talc	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg	5mg

Fig no.2 Sustained release formulated tablets

PRE FORMULATION STUDIES

1. **ANGLE OF REPOSE**-Angle of repose is the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of powder and horizontal plane.

$$\tan \theta = \frac{h}{r}$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{h}{r}$$

Where h is the height of heap, r is the radius of heap

Lower the Angle of repose, better the flow property of given powder. Rough and irregular surface of particle gives higher angle of repose.

ii. **BULK DENSITY (pb)**: It is defined as mass of powder divided by Bulk volume. Bulk volume is defined as the volume of particles including inter and intra particle spaces. It gives valuable information about tablet's porosity and its evident relationship to Hardness and Disintegration. It may be used to check Uniformity of bulk chemicals. It can also be used to determine proper size of containers, mixing apparatus and types of capsules for given mass of powder.

Bulk Density (pb) = Weight of powder(W)/Bulk volume(vb)

Tapping Method for Bulk Density Determination:

Weight accurately about 10 grams of given powder. Transfer it in a dry measuring cylinder and drop the cylinder 2-3 times and measure the volume(V_0) After getting initial bulk volume, drop the cylinder 100 times from fixed height, the volume remains constant and hence measure the tapped Bulk volume.

iii) TAPPED DENSITY:

The weighed tablet mixture had been poured into a graduated cylinder. It was noted the quantity of drug was present. The cylinder was then subjected to 100, 200, and 300 taps in a tap density device. USP states that it was stated by.

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder}}{\text{Tapped volume of the powder}}$$

iv) HAUSNERS RATIO:

It is a measurement of the frictional resistance of the tablet composition. The ideal range should be between 1.2 and 1.5, The ratio of tap density was used to estimate it.

$$\text{Hausners ratio} = \frac{\text{tapped density}}{\text{poured density}}$$

V) CARR'S INDEX:

The Hausners ratio and compressibility index were utilized to determine Capabilities, the change in volume that arises from packing Rearrangement during tapping was used. And it was determined by

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density(pb)} - \text{Bulk Density (pb)}}{\text{Tapped density (pt)}} \times 100$$

D) POST FORMULATION STUDIES:

i) **THICKNESS**: The thickness and diameter of a tablet are measured using Vernier Calipers or screw gauge. With the help of Vernier caliper thickness and diameter of five tablets were used for above test from each batch checked on results were expressed in millimeters (mm).

ii)HARDNESS:

The force is measure in kg/cm² and hardness of 4kg/cm² is consider. To be satisfactory for uncoated tablet. Erwcka tester, Schleuniger tester And strong cobb tester are used for tablet hardness testing. The acceptable limit of hardness of a tablet is 5-8kg. Beside, a force Between 4 and 10kg is also considered to be satisfactory. Place the tablet between the jaws of Monsanto hardness tester and slowly Go on rotating the screw until the tablet break. Note down the reading and repeat the procedure for 5 tablets.

UNIFOMITY OF WEIGHT (weight variation test):

weigh 20 tablets selected at random and calculate the average weight. Tablet were weighed individually and the percentage of deviation of its Weight from the average weight was determined for each tablet. Not More than two of the individuals weight derivate from the average Weight derivate from the average weight by more than the percentage and Shown in the following table and none deviates by more than twice Percentage.

iii) Friabilator:

Friability of the tablet was determined using Roche Friabilator. The device Subjects the tablets to the combined effect of abrasion and shock in aplastic Chamber resolving at 25 rpm tablet to the combined effect of abrasion and shock in a plastic chamber resolving. Pre weighed sample of tablets at a height of 6 inches in each revolution. Pre weighed sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator and were subjected to 100 revolutions. Tablets were dedusted using a soft muslin cloth and weighed.

The friability (f)is given by the formula.

$$\text{Friability (f)} = \frac{1-w_1}{w_2} \times 100$$

vii) In-vitro Dissolution studies:

The release rate of formulated ritonavir sustain release tablets Were determined by using the United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) dissolution testing apparatus II. 900 ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer is used as dissolution medium. A single tablet is placed in each basket. The temperature of the dissolution system is maintained at 37 degree and rotation of the basket is maintained at 50 rpm for 12hrs. The 6 samples were withdrawn from each of the basket at the following time interval 0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12. An equipment volume of the fresh dissolution fluid is replenished after each sampling time interval. Filter the sample is required 1ml is taken and made up to 10ml with buffer. The absorbance of all the samples is measured at 239nm by UV-spectrophotometer.

RESULT AND DISSCUSSION:

Pre formulation studies:-

Table no.2 Pre formulation characterization studies

Formulations	Angle of repose	Bulk density	Tapped density	Compressibility index	Hausners ratio
F1	25.6	0.43	0.50	21.6	1.25
F2	21.8	0.50	0.46	20.21	1.32
F3	25.64	0.47	0.58	21.6	1.23
F4	21.01	0.38	0.51	21.12	1.26
F5	24.4	0.41	0.52	22.31	1.24
F6	29.09w	0.45	0.52	18.18	1.22

Post compression characteristics of ritonavir sustain release tablet:

The tablets with a weight of 500mg were prepared and subjected to the quality control test such as weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, in vitro dissolution studies etc...and the values are recorded. All the formulations lied in the pharmacopoeial requirement within+5 for weight variation of 500mg. the drug contain for the formulation found to be uniform.

Table no.3 Post formulation characterization studies

S.No	Formulations	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability
1.	F1	4.3	6.1	0.5
2.	F2	4.2	5.9	0.62
3.	F3	4.6	6.2	0.45
4.	F4	4.4	6.2	0.58
5.	F5	4.1	6.1	0.78
6.	F6	4.1	5.9	0.86

Weight variation studies

Table no.4 Weight variation studies (F1 to F6)

SL.NO	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1.	500mg	500mg	490mg	490mg	500mg	498mg
2.	497mg	496mg	500mg	500mg	500mg	500mg
3.	484mg	500mg	490mg	500mg	496mg	499mg
4.	496mg	500mg	500mg	499mg	500mg	489mg
5.	500mg	486mg	486mg	500mg	490mg	500mg
6.	490mg	500mg	500mg	500mg	487mg	496mg
7.	497mg	500mg	500mg	499mg	499mg	500mg
8.	499mg	499mg	496mg	500mg	500mg	499mg
9.	500mg	500mg	500mg	498mg	500mg	500mg
10.	494mg	486mg	499mg	500mg	498mg	499mg

STANDARD CALIBRATION CURVE OF RITONAVIR SUSTAIN RELEASE TABLET BY 6.8 PHOSPHATE BUFFER

Table no.5 Standard value calibration of ritonavir tablet by 6.8 phosphate buffer

SL.NO	Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	10µg/ml	0.148
3	20µg/ml	0.322
4	30µg/ml	0.485
5	40µg/ml	0.672
6	50µg/ml	0.816
7	60µg/ml	0.991

Fig no.3 Calibration curve of ritonavir by using UV method

CALIBRATION CURVE OF RITONAVIR SUSTAIN RELEASE TABLET BY 0.1N HCl:

Table no.6 Standard values calibration of ritonavir tablet by 0.1N HCl

SL.NO	Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	10µg/ml	0.08
3	20µg/ml	0.28
4	30µg/ml	0.50
5	40µg/ml	0.74

6	50µg/ml	0.95
7	60µg/ml	1.2

Fig no.4 Calibration curve of ritonavir tablet by UV method

Calculation formula for percentage drug release determination

Concentration (in 10ml) in mg = concentration /10

Concentration (in 90 ml) in mg = concentration in 10ml/10 x 900

Cumulative concentration in 900ml= concentration in 900ml-previous values of cumulative concentration in 10ml

Percentage drug release= cumulative concentration in 900ml /Amount of drug in mg (300mg)

In vitro dissolution studies:

Percentage drug release for formulation F1 TO F6

Table no.7: Percentage drug release for formulation F1 to F6

S.no	Time in Hrs	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	25.22	20.41	21.99	16.71	19.62	27.61
2	2	27.24	28.61	32.28	23.10	26.02	38.4
3	3	36.21	37.01	39.02	29.08	33.26	47.18
4	4	44.49	45.05	45.83	37.06	38.08	56.08
5	5	53.26	53.38	49.81	44.08	42.08	64.68
6	6	59.61	60.75	55.06	51.8	46.81	71.40
7	7	64.12	69.75	61.31	59.06	50.56	77.61
8	8	68.06	78.18	65.20	66.37	55.23	80.87
9	9	73.12	84.93	69.18	72.57	61.31	84.02
10	10	78.18	89.43	73.67	79.50	66.37	84.04
11	11	87.43	92.82	78.31	87.72	72.56	89.01
12	12	90.63	95.64	84.27	90.22	77.62	90.01

Comparison graph of percentage drug release for formulation F1 to F6

Fig no.5 Comparison graph of percentage drug release for ritonavir sustained release formulations F1 to F6

Comparison graph of percentage drug release for formulation F1 and F2

Fig no.6 Comparison graph of percentage drug release for optimized ritonavir sustained release tablet formulation F1 & F2 in the presence of polymer (HPMC)

CONCLUSION

The present aim of the study is to develop sustain release matrix tablets of Ritonavir prepared by wet granulation method using controlled release polymer i.e., HPMC, Ethyl cellulose and carbopol. The drug (300mg) was mixed with polymer and excipients and compressed into tablets (500mg) for these six formulations are designed i.e F1,F2,F3,F4,F5,F6, with varying concentration of polymer in each formulation. The pre-formulation parameters are performed angle of repose was less than 40° and compressibility index/cares index was less than 23 for all the formulations including good to fair flow ability and compressibility. Hausner ratio was found to be approximately 1 to 1.25 for all the batches indicating good flow property. The evaluation parameters are performed and results were satisfactory and within the acceptable limits for the uniformity of weight, hardness, thickness, friability. The formulation F1,F2 were prepared by HPLC (hydrophilic polymer) as a rate controlling polymer with two different ratio: 50mg, 75mg of total weight of tablet the in vitro drug release were found to be 90.36%, 95.64% for 12hrs respectively. The formulation F3,F4 were prepared by carbopol as a rate controlling polymer with 2 different ratio: 50mg, 75mg of total weight of tablet which shows the decreasing release of 84.27%, 90.22%, till the end of 12hours. The formulation F5,F6 were prepared by EC (hydrophobic polymer) as a rate controlling polymer with some two different ratio: 50mg, 75mg of total weight of tablet. The in vitro drug release were found to be 77.62% and 90.01%. The drug release was found to be lowest with EC, because as EC was extensively hydrophobic in nature with lower wettability, didn't occur to facilitate extend drug release. From all the prepared sustained release tablet of Ritonavir, it was concluded that F2 formulation

showed better sustained decreasing release from the dosage form 95.64% for 12hours. From in vitro release study revealed that increasing concentration of polymer, retarded The drug release, and the results conformed that the release rate from Ritonavir sustained release tablet depends upon the concentration of polymer.

REFERENCES:

1. SC Marapur, D S Pattanshetty, Prashant Jorapur, M Chetan, S M Biradar, Formulation Development and Evaluation of Sustained Release Tablets of Mercaptopurine, Marapur et al., RJPS 2020;10(2):32-38.
2. Gambhire MN, Ambade KW, Kurmi SD, Kadam VJ, Jadhav KR. Development and in vitro evaluation of an oral floating matrix tablet formulation of diltiazem hydrochloride. AAPS Pharm Sci Tech. 2007;8:E73. doi: 10.1208/pt0803073. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
3. Gordon ER, Rosanke TW, Fonner OE, Anderson NR, Baker GS. Pharmaceutical dosage forms: Tablets. In: Lieberman HA, Lachman L, Schwartz, editors. New York: Marcel Dekker; 1990. p. 83. [Google Scholar]
4. Vayas SP, Khar RK. 1st ed. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan; 2002. Controlled drug delivery concepts and advances; p. 100. [Google Scholar]
5. Reddy KR, Mutalik S, Reddy S. Once-daily sustained release matrix tablets of nicorandil: Formulation and in vitro valuation. AAPS Pharm Sci Tech. 2003;4:E61. doi: 10.1208/pt040461. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Siddique S, Mohd Y. Formulation of sustained release matrix of highly water soluble drugs. Pharma Review. 2008 [Google Scholar]
7. King RE. Tablets in remington's pharmaceutical sciences. In: Coy MP, editor. 15th ed. Vol. 1. Pennsylvania: 1975. [Google Scholar]
8. Jain NK. 1st ed. Vol. 1. CBS Publishers and Distributers; 1975. Pharmaceutical Product Development"; pp. 420–21. (428-29). [Google Scholar]
9. Krishnaiyah YS, Karthikeyan RS, Gouri Sankar V, Satyanarayana V. Three-layer guar gum matrix tablet formulations for oral controlled delivery of highly soluble trimetazidine dihydrochloride. J Control Release. 2002;81:45–56. doi: 10.1016/s0168-3659(02)00031-7. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Subal CB, Kesevan SK, Murugesan R. Design and release characteristics of sustained release tablet containing metformin HCl. Braz J Pharm Sci. 2008;44:477–83. [Google Scholar]
11. Velmurugan S, Ali M, Kumar P. Microparticulate drug carriers: A promising approach for the delivery of anti HIV drugs. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci 2014;6(2):31-9.8.
12. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ritonavir>
13. Kenneth N, Parthasarathy V, Manavalan R, Narendra C. AmJ PharmTech Res 2012;2(6):231-44.